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Studying the Impact of Perceived Organizational Justice (POJ) on Employee Engagement (EE): An Empirical Study on the Mediating Role of Organizational Trust (OT)

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Abstract

the purpose of this study is to examine the extent to which Perceived Organizational Justice (POJ) comprising of distributive, procedural, and interactional justice, affects Employee Engagement (EE) in Egypt's manufacturing sector, and to investigate the mediating role of Organizational Trust (OT) in this relationship. The study seeks to address the existing gap in literature concerning the influence of fairness perceptions on engagement within the Egyptian manufacturing sector context, where socio-economic and cultural factors distinctly shape workplace dynamics. The study adopts a quantitative research methodology, employing structured survey instruments to collect primary data from employees in Egypt's manufacturing industry. Measurement tools include Colquitt's Organizational Justice Scale (2001) for POJ, Gallup's Q12 Engagement Scale (2023) for EE, and Mayer and Davis's Organizational Trust Scale (1999) for OT. The collected data are analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) and Regression Analysis to test hypothesized relationships and the mediating effect of trust. The findings reveal that all three dimensions of perceived organizational justice, distributive, procedural, and interactional, significantly and positively influence both organizational trust and employee engagement. Moreover, organizational trust is found to play a partial mediating role in the relationship between justice and engagement. The contribution of this study lies in its theoretical and contextual originality. It offers a culturally grounded examination of fairness perceptions in Egypt's manufacturing sector, providing a framework for managers and policymakers to foster justice-driven engagement strategies.

Keywords: Perceived Organizational Justice (POJ), Perceived Distributive Organizational Justice (PDOJ), Perceived Procedural Organizational Justice (PPOJ), Perceived Interactional Organizational Justice (PIOJ), Employee Engagement (EE), Organizational Trust (OT), Counterproductive Work Behavior (CWB), Social Exchange Theory (SET), Structural Equation Modeling (SEM).

Introduction

Employee engagement is a central driver of organizational and societal outcomes. Highly engaged employees are more productive, innovative, and committed, which translates into stronger business performance and broader contributions to community well-being and corporate social responsibility (CSR) activities (Aguinis & Glavas, 2012; Harter, Schmidt, & Hayes, 2002). Engagement is strongly shaped by employees' perceptions of fairness in the workplace captured by the construct of perceived organizational justice (POJ).

Perceived organizational justice refers to employees' subjective perceptions of fairness in outcomes, procedures, and interpersonal treatment (Greenberg, 1990). Literature typically distinguishes three dimensions: distributive justice (fairness of outcomes such as pay and promotions), procedural justice (fairness of decision-making procedures), and interactional justice (fairness, respect, and adequacy of interpersonal treatment and explanations; Colquitt et al., 2001; Bies & Moag, 1986). When employees perceive high levels of justice, they

report higher job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and engagement, and are more likely to display organizational citizenship behaviors (OCBs) and innovative work behaviors (Cropanzano, Bowen, & Gilliland, 2007; Nazir et al., 2019). Conversely, injustice is associated with turnover intentions, deviance, and counterproductive work behavior (CWB; Greenberg, 1990).

Recent work shows that perceived organizational justice enhances innovative work behavior indirectly through work engagement, highlighting engagement as a key psychological mechanism linking fairness to positive outcomes (Lin, Beh, & Kamil, 2024). In parallel, research on social exchange suggests that when employees perceive a fair exchange between their contributions and rewards, they reciprocate through higher engagement and extra-role behavior (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005). Perceptions of justice therefore function as important antecedents of engagement rather than merely outcomes of other processes (Saks, 2006).

Organizational trust is another critical construct in this nexus. Trust in the organization, a willingness to be vulnerable based on expectations of integrity, benevolence, and competence (Mayer, Davis, & Schoorman, 1995). This is consistently linked to job satisfaction, commitment, and performance (Dirks & Ferrin, 2002). Justice perceptions are among the primary drivers of trust: fair procedures, respectful treatment, and transparent communication foster employees' confidence that the organization will act in their best interest (Colquitt, Scott, & LePine, 2007).

This study focuses on the interplay between perceived organizational justice (POJ), organizational trust (OT), and employee engagement (EE) in the manufacturing industry in Egypt. The central premise is that POJ enhances EE both directly and indirectly through OT. Organizations that cultivate fairness and trust not only improve performance and retention but also contribute to broader societal goals such as economic stability, ethical business conduct, and social inclusion (Aguinis & Glavas, 2012). In Egypt's manufacturing sector—an important engine of GDP, employment, and industrial modernization—these dynamics are especially salient.

Research Problem and Gap

Prior studies have established significant relationships between POJ and EE, as well as between justice and outcomes such as performance, OCB, and turnover intentions (Colquitt et al., 2001, 2013; Saks, 2006). More recently, work has underscored the link between justice and engagement and recommended further exploration across industries and cultures (Ghosh, Rai, & Sinha, 2014; Macey & Schneider, 2008).

However, several gaps remain understudied; Dimensional **interaction is one of them**, Research has not sufficiently clarified how the three dimensions of justice jointly shape engagement. Evidence suggests distributive and interactional justice may have stronger direct effects on engagement than procedural justice, but mechanisms remain underexplored (Ghosh et al., 2014; Mubashar et al., 2022). **Contextual gap is another one, Egyptian manufacturing**, Most justice–engagement work has been conducted in Western or service settings. There is limited empirical research on how POJ influences EE in the manufacturing sector in Egypt, despite this sector's central role in employment and GDP (Abdel-Maksoud, 2013; Elamin & Tlaiss, 2015). **Role of organizational trust as mediator** is also underexplored, although trust is often mentioned as a mechanism through which justice affects attitudes and behaviors, comparatively fewer studies have modeled OT explicitly as a mediator between POJ and EE, especially in Middle Eastern manufacturing settings (Aryee, Budhwar, & Chen, 2002; Dirks & Ferrin, 2002).

These gaps are significant because Egypt's manufacturing sector is experiencing rapid change and contributes substantially to economic growth and employment. Ensuring that growth is accompanied by fair labor practices and high engagement is critical for sustainable and inclusive development.

Problem Statement

To what extent does Perceived Organizational Justice (POJ) affect Employee Engagement (EE)? Does Organizational Trust (OT) mediate the relationship between POJ and EE?

Research Questions

1. To what extent do the three dimensions of perceived organizational justice (distributive, procedural, interactional) influence employee engagement?
2. How do these three dimensions affect employees' trust in the organization?
3. To what extent does organizational trust enhance employee engagement?
4. Does organizational trust mediate the relationship between perceived distributive organizational justice and employee engagement?
5. Does organizational trust mediate the relationship between perceived procedural organizational justice and employee engagement?
6. Does organizational trust mediate the relationship between perceived interactional organizational justice and employee engagement?

Hypotheses

The study proposes six hypotheses:

H1: There is a significant positive relationship between the three dimensions of perceived organizational justice (POJ) and employee engagement (EE).

H2: There is a significant positive relationship between the three dimensions of POJ and organizational trust (OT).

H3: There is a significant positive relationship between OT and EE.

H4: Perceived distributive organizational justice (PDOJ) has a significant relationship with OT, which mediates the relationship between PDOJ and EE.

H5: Perceived procedural organizational justice (PPOJ) has a significant relationship with OT, which mediates the relationship between PPOJ and EE.

H6: Perceived interactional organizational justice (PIOJ) has a significant relationship with OT, which mediates the relationship between PIOJ and EE.

Study Significance

Academic Significance

The study advances several streams of literature; Justice as antecedent, not outcome; by positioning POJ as an independent variable and EE as the dependent variable, the research clarifies the causal chain from justice to engagement and further to counterproductive work behavior (CWB). While many studies correlate justice with CWB, fewer examine how justice shapes engagement, which in turn inhibits deviance (Tahir et al., 2022; Mubashar et al., 2022).

Integration of positive and negative behavior literatures; Modeling justice, engagement, and CWB bridges traditionally separate domains: positive behaviors (engagement, OCB) and negative behaviors (deviance, withdrawal). This allows more comprehensive explanations of how fair treatment both energizes employees and reduces harmful conduct.

Contextual contribution: by focusing on Egypt's manufacturing sector, the study provides context-specific evidence from a non-Western, emerging-economy setting where rapid industrial expansion coexists with concerns about equity, working conditions, and institutional reforms.

Theoretical refinement: The study applies and integrates Social Exchange Theory, the Job Demands–Resources (JD-R) model, and fairness heuristic perspectives to explain how justice perceptions translate into trust and engagement (Adams, 1965; Bakker & Demerouti, 2007; Lind, 2001).

Practical Significance

Reducing CWB through fairness and engagement; Perceived injustice often triggers negative emotions (anger, resentment) and can lead to CWB such as sabotage, theft, or withdrawal. Fairness in outcomes, procedures, and interaction reduces these risks by elevating engagement and trust. High-leverage managerial levers; Interventions that improve justice perceptions, such as transparent decision processes, consistent application of rules, respectful communication, and meaningful voice, are relatively actionable and can simultaneously enhance engagement and reduce deviance.

Strategic alignment with industrial policy; In Egypt, manufacturing accounts for a sizable share of GDP and employment. Justice in wages, promotion, safety, and gender equality strengthens human capital, attracts investment, and supports inclusive growth agendas such as Egypt's Vision 2030.

Employer branding and retention; In a tight labor market, organizations that are perceived as fair and trustworthy are better able to attract and retain talent, lowering recruitment costs and stabilizing skill pipelines.

Literature Review

This chapter synthesizes theoretical and empirical work on employee engagement, perceived organizational justice, and organizational trust. It develops an integrated model in which the three dimensions of justice influence engagement directly and indirectly via trust, with a focus on manufacturing settings and the Egyptian context.

Employee Engagement

Employee engagement is defined as a positive, fulfilling, work-related state of mind characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption (Schaufeli, Salanova, González-Romá, & Bakker, 2002). Vigor reflects high energy and mental resilience; dedication reflects a sense of significance, enthusiasm, and challenge; and absorption denotes being fully concentrated and happily engrossed in one's work (Bakker & Demerouti, 2008).

Antecedents of engagement; the Job Demands–Resources (JD-R) model posits that job resources (e.g., autonomy, social support, feedback) and personal resources (e.g., self-efficacy, optimism) are key predictors of engagement (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007; Xanthopoulou et al., 2007). Social Exchange Theory adds that employees engage more deeply when they perceive a fair exchange between their efforts and the rewards they receive (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005). Justice perceptions thus function as critical job resources.

Outcomes of engagement; high engagement is consistently linked to higher performance, creativity, OCB, and customer satisfaction, as well as lower absenteeism, turnover intentions, and burnout (Harter et al., 2002; Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004; Saks, 2006). A large-scale meta-analysis at the business-unit level showed that employee satisfaction/engagement is positively related to productivity, profit, customer satisfaction, and safety, and negatively related to turnover and accidents (Harter et al., 2002).

Despite its popularity, engagement remains conceptually debated. Some scholars question whether it is distinct from job involvement, job satisfaction, or organizational commitment (Macey & Schneider, 2008). There are also measurement issues (e.g., different scales and factor structures). Nonetheless, there is broad consensus that engagement captures a more energetic, investment-oriented state than traditional attitudes and is a crucial predictor of individual and organizational success. Given its importance, understanding how organizational factors, particularly fairness and trust, shape engagement is a central concern of this study.

Perceived Organizational Justice

Perceived organizational justice captures employees' judgments about fairness in their organization's outcomes, procedures, and interpersonal treatment (Greenberg, 1990). The dominant framework distinguishes three dimensions (Colquitt et al., 2001):

Distributive justice, perceived fairness of outcome distributions (e.g., pay, promotions, workload). Drawing on equity theory, employees compare their input–outcome ratios to those of others; perceived inequity leads to distress and attempts to restore balance (Adams, 1965).

Procedural justice, perceived fairness of the processes used to arrive at decisions. Fair procedures are consistent across people and time, unbiased, accurate, correctable, representative (provide voice), and ethical (Leventhal, 1980).

Interactional justice, perceived fairness in interpersonal treatment and explanations during the implementation of procedures. Bies and Moag (1986) emphasized respect, dignity, politeness, and adequate, truthful information as key criteria.

These dimensions are conceptually distinct but strongly correlated, and together they shape global fairness judgments (Colquitt et al., 2001).

Theoretical lenses. Several theories explain why justice matters.

Equity theory, unfair outcomes create psychological tension, leading employees to adjust their input (e.g., effort) or seek alternative employment (Adams, 1965).

Social Exchange Theory, fair treatment signals organizational support, prompting employees to reciprocate with positive attitudes and behaviors (Blau, 1964; Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005).

Fairness heuristic theory, in uncertain environments, employees use justice cues (distributive, procedural, interactional) to form a fairness “heuristic” that guides trust and cooperation (Lind, 2001; Colquitt, 2012).

Empirical findings

Meta-analytic evidence shows that all three justice dimensions are positively related to job satisfaction, organizational commitment, task performance, OCB, and negatively related to turnover intentions and CWB (Colquitt et al., 2001, 2013; Rosiński, 2015). Procedural and interactional justice often emerge as especially strong predictors of trust and commitment because they convey information about the organization's values and respect for employees (Colquitt et al., 2001; Bies, 2005). Justice climates, shared perceptions of fairness at the team or organizational level, also predict collective outcomes such as team performance and innovation.

In addition to attitudinal and behavioral outcomes, chronic perceived injustice is associated with negative health outcomes, including stress, depression, and cardiovascular risk (Elovainio et al., 2006), underscoring the human cost of unfair work environments.

Organizational Trust

Organizational trust refers to employees' willingness to be vulnerable to the organization (and its leaders) based on positive expectations of its intentions and behavior (Mayer et al., 1995). Trust involves cognitive judgments about competence and reliability, as well as affective components such as emotional security and identification (Dirks & Ferrin, 2002).

Leadership behavior, transparency, consistency, and ethical leadership behaviors build trust (Burke et al., 2007). Justice perceptions, fair procedures, equitable outcomes, and respectful treatment signal integrity and benevolence, thereby enhancing trust (Colquitt et al., 2007). In addition, Interpersonal relations,

cooperative, supportive relationships and open communication among colleagues foster a trusting climate (McAllister, 1995).

Consequently, trust in the organization is linked to higher job satisfaction, organizational commitment, OCB, and performance, and to lower turnover intentions (Dirks & Ferrin, 2002; Laschinger, Finegan, & Wilk, 2009). A meta-analysis on trust in leadership found robust positive associations with work attitudes, intentions, and performance (Dirks & Ferrin, 2002).

Critically for this study, OT is a strong predictor of engagement: when employees trust their organization and leaders, they feel safe investing their physical, cognitive, and emotional energies into their work (Kahn, 1990; Macey & Schneider, 2008). This positions OT as a plausible mediator between POJ and EE.

Distributive Justice, Trust, and Engagement

Distributive justice involves employees' perceptions of how fairly rewards and resources are allocated. Fair distributions signal that the organization values employees' contributions, which fosters feelings of respect and recognition and strengthens trust (Colquitt et al., 2001; Mayer et al., 1995).

Empirical research shows that distributive justice predicts job satisfaction, commitment, and engagement, and is negatively related to turnover intentions (Mustofa, 2022; Ghosh et al., 2014). When employees believe that pay, promotions, and recognition are fairly aligned with effort and performance, they are more likely to feel psychologically invested and willing to exert discretionary effort (Cropanzano & Rupp, 2003).

Organizational trust mediates this relationship: perceptions of fair distribution build trust in the organization's integrity, which, in turn, fuels engagement. Studies have found that trust can fully or partially mediate the effects of distributive justice on engagement and related outcomes such as commitment (Alvi & Abbasi, 2012; Agarwal, 2014). This logic underpins **H4**, which posits a mediated relationship between perceived distributive organizational justice, OT, and EE.

Procedural Justice, Trust, and Engagement

Procedural justice pertains to the fairness of decision-making processes (Leventhal, 1980; Lind & Tyler, 1988). Employees value voice, consistency, bias-free procedures, accurate information, and mechanisms for appeal. Fair procedures convey that the organization respects employees and is committed to equitable treatment over time, even when particular outcomes are unfavorable.

Procedural justice is often a stronger predictor of trust and commitment than distributive justice, because it speaks to the stability and moral character of the organization (Colquitt et al., 2001; Greenberg, 1990). When employees perceive that processes are fair, they are more likely to accept negative outcomes, maintain loyalty, and continue investing effort.

Studies indicate that procedural justice has both direct and indirect effects on engagement. Saks (2006) showed that justice perceptions (especially procedural) significantly predict engagement, and that trust mediates part of this effect. Aryee et al. (2002) found that trust fully mediated the link between procedural justice and outcomes such as satisfaction and commitment.

Thus, procedural justice shapes engagement by building a sense of psychological safety, legitimacy, and shared purpose—mechanisms that are captured through OT. This reasoning supports **H5**, which posits that OT mediates the relationship between perceived procedural organizational justice and EE.

Interactional Justice, Trust, and Engagement

Interactional justice refers to the quality of interpersonal treatment and adequacy of explanations employees receive from authorities (Bies & Moag, 1986). Being treated with dignity, respect, and honesty strongly influences how employees interpret both procedures and outcomes.

Because day-to-day interactions are highly salient, interactional justice can have powerful effects on attitudes and behavior. Disrespectful or humiliating treatment can undermine even objectively fair procedures, whereas respectful treatment can buffer the negative impact of unfavorable outcomes (Cohen-Charash & Spector, 2001; Bies, 2005).

Interactional justice is closely tied to trust: respectful and transparent communication signals benevolence and integrity, which are core components of trust (Mayer et al., 1995). Empirical work shows that fair interpersonal treatment enhances OT, which in turn promotes engagement, commitment, and OCB and reduces CWB (Brashear et al., 2003; Cho & Park, 2011; Mubashar et al., 2022).

Accordingly, **H6** proposes that OT mediates the relationship between perceived interactional organizational justice and EE.

Justice, Engagement, and Counterproductive Work Behavior

Beyond positive outcomes, justice and engagement also relate to the reduction of negative behaviors. Perceived injustice, whether in outcomes, procedures, or interactional treatment, can trigger emotional reactions such as anger and resentment, often interpreted as violations of the psychological contract (Cochran, 2014; Barsky et al., 2011). These reactions may lead to CWB, including sabotage, theft, withdrawal, and interpersonal deviance.

Research has documented negative associations between justice dimensions and CWB, and emerging evidence suggests engagement can mediate part of this effect: fair treatment enhances engagement, and engaged employees are less likely to retaliate or withdraw (Tahir et al., 2022; Adugna et al., 2022; Saks, 2006). This study's conceptualization of POJ as an antecedent of EE implicitly adopts this broader chain: justice, trust, engagement, and reduced CWB.

Justice and Inclusive Industrial Development in Egypt

Finally, the justice–engagement nexus must be understood within Egypt's manufacturing context. Manufacturing represents a major contributor to GDP and employment and has shown strong recent growth in non-petroleum sectors such as garments, automotive, and electronics. At the same time, the sector faces challenges related to working conditions, wage fairness, and regional and gender disparities.

In this environment, organizational justice is not solely an internal HR concern; it is a strategic enabler of inclusive growth. Fair labor practices, transparent governance, and ethical resource allocation support social stability, reduce unrest, and encourage local and foreign investment. Justice at the organizational level thus supports national objectives related to Egypt's Vision 2030 by aligning economic performance with social cohesion and equity.

Conceptual Framework

Perceived organizational justice (distributive, procedural, interactional) is a multidimensional antecedent that shapes employees' global fairness judgments. These fairness perceptions foster organizational trust, a key psychological state characterized by willingness to be vulnerable based on beliefs in organizational integrity, benevolence, and competence. Trust, in turn, energizes employee engagement, vigor, dedication, and absorption, which drives performance, innovation, and retention and reduces deviance. The relationships may vary by justice dimension, with distributive justice particularly salient for reward fairness, procedural justice for legitimacy and commitment, and interactional justice for daily experiences of respect.

Grounded in Social Exchange Theory, JD-R, equity theory, and fairness heuristic perspectives, the proposed model treats POJ as the primary independent construct, OT as the mediator, and EE as the focal outcome, tested in the under-researched context of Egypt's manufacturing industry.

Conceptual Framework:

Figure (3.1) Conceptual Framework

Theoretical Framework

Employee engagement has long been recognized as a central driver of organizational success, and several foundational theories help explain how engagement emerges and is sustained in the workplace. Social Exchange Theory (SET) provides an essential lens for understanding these dynamics. According to SET, employee engagement is shaped by reciprocal exchanges between the employee and the organization, such that when employees perceive support, fairness, and recognition, they respond with commitment, engagement, and positive discretionary effort (Blau, 1964).

This reciprocal pattern underscores an important psychological mechanism: employees who believe they are treated fairly and respectfully are more likely to reciprocate through enhanced performance and dedication. SET therefore strengthens the conceptual foundation for examining how justice perceptions influence engagement.

The Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) model offers a complementary explanation by conceptualizing engagement as the product of available job resources that offset job demands (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007). Job resources such as autonomy, supervisory support, feedback, and growth opportunities stimulate engagement, particularly when employees face demanding work conditions. Personal resources, including optimism and resilience, further amplify engagement by helping employees cope with workplace pressures. In this model, when organizations provide adequate resources and eliminate excessive demands, employee engagement increases, translating into improved performance, reduced burnout, and stronger organizational commitment.

Self-Determination Theory (SDT) introduces an additional perspective by emphasizing intrinsic motivation and the satisfaction of basic psychological needs. According to SDT, employees become engaged when their needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness are fulfilled (Deci & Ryan, 2000). Autonomy supports

employees' sense of control, competence promotes feelings of mastery, and relatedness strengthens interpersonal connections at work. SDT therefore explains why work environments characterized by trust, fairness, and support naturally foster higher levels of employee engagement.

The Fairness Heuristic Theory further contributes insights into how employees form fairness judgments under conditions of uncertainty. According to this framework, individuals use procedural, distributive, and interpersonal cues to make holistic fairness assessments (Lind & Van den Bos, 2001). Early in organizational interactions, procedural and interactional justice cues dramatically shape fairness judgments because outcomes may not yet be observable (Colquitt, 2012). Thus, employees rely heavily on signals of respect, transparency, and unbiased procedures to determine whether authorities are trustworthy.

Collectively, these theories present a comprehensive foundation for understanding the mechanisms through which organizations cultivate engagement. SET highlights the role of perceived reciprocity, JD-R emphasizes the significance of workplace resources, SDT focuses on intrinsic motivation, and Fairness Heuristic Theory underscores the importance of early justice cues. Together, these frameworks suggest that organizations must foster fairness across processes, interactions, and outcomes to build trust and sustain long-term engagement. Because engagement directly influences performance, innovation, and customer satisfaction (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007), studying these mechanisms is vital for organizational success.

Perceived Organizational Justice and Employee Engagement

Recent research has expanded the understanding of perceived organizational justice by identifying the multifaceted ways employees evaluate fairness within their organizations. Contemporary justice research synthesizes perspectives from procedural, distributive, interpersonal, and informational justice to explain why employees respond positively, or negatively, to workplace environments (Benabdelhadi, 2023). Perceived injustice has been shown to trigger counterproductive outcomes, including absenteeism, reduced performance, stress, and turnover (Dosanjh & Rao, 2020), reinforcing the need for fair practices.

SET remains a core theoretical foundation linking justice perceptions to engagement. When employees perceive that supervisors and the organization treat them fairly, they reciprocate with stronger engagement and organizational citizenship behaviors (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005). The JD-R model similarly aligns with justice research because perceived fairness functions as a crucial job resource. Fair treatment satisfies employees' need for respect, voice, and inclusion, thereby motivating engagement and mitigating burnout in demanding conditions (Demerouti et al., 2001). Fair procedures and interactions thus operate as resources that promote positive workplace functioning.

Integrating SET and JD-R reveals how justice perceptions influence engagement both directly and indirectly. Fair treatment not only fulfills psychological needs but also strengthens trust, which fosters a positive exchange relationship between the employee and the organization (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007; Saks, 2006). This integration provides the conceptual foundation for examining how perceived organizational justice enhances engagement through organizational trust.

Conceptual Framework Overview

The conceptual model developed for this study incorporates perceived organizational justice (POJ) as the independent variable, employee engagement (EE) as the dependent variable, and organizational trust (OT) as the mediating variable. The three dimensions of POJ—distributive, procedural, and interactional justice—are theorized to influence EE both directly and indirectly through OT. This framework operationalizes SET's principles of reciprocity, JD-R's focus on resources such as fairness and support, and SDT's emphasis on interpersonal respect and autonomy. It also models the fairness heuristic process, wherein fairness cues inform trust assessments that subsequently shape engagement.

Hypotheses Development

Drawing on SET, JD-R, SDT, and the justice literature, six hypotheses were formulated. The first predicts a significant positive relationship between the three dimensions of perceived organizational justice and employee engagement. The second proposes a positive relationship between the same justice dimensions and organizational trust. The third hypothesizes that organizational trust positively influences engagement. The final three hypotheses examine whether organizational trust mediates the relationships between distributive, procedural, and interactional justice and employee engagement. These hypotheses collectively test the structural relationships embedded within the conceptual framework.

The Manufacturing Sector in Egypt: An Overview

The manufacturing sector in Egypt plays a central role in national economic development, contributing significantly to GDP, exports, and employment (Mahmoud, 2012). Historically, Egypt's industrial development began in the nineteenth century under Muhammad Ali Pasha and expanded substantially during the mid-twentieth century through state-led initiatives under President Gamal Abdel Nasser (El-Mahdi, 2002). Today, the sector spans traditional industries such as textiles and food processing as well as advanced sectors including chemicals, electronics, pharmaceuticals, and automotive manufacturing (Abdel-Maksoud, 2013).

Textiles and apparel remain among Egypt's most important industrial pillars due to the country's high-quality cotton and strong export capacity (World Bank, 2020). The food and beverage industry has also expanded, driven by rising domestic demand and technological upgrades (CAPMAS, 2023). Meanwhile, the automotive sector has benefited from favorable government policies and increased foreign investment (Oxford Business Group, 2021), and chemical and pharmaceutical industries continue to maintain significant economic influence (ICIS, 2022). Electronics manufacturing is also emerging rapidly, supported by both domestic and international investment (African Development Bank, 2021).

Despite its strengths, the sector faces notable challenges, including regulatory inefficiencies, infrastructure gaps, bureaucratic hurdles, and misalignment between educational outputs and industry needs (IMF, 2022; OECD, 2019). High energy costs and inconsistent enforcement of industrial policies impede stable growth, while macroeconomic instability, inflation, and fluctuating exchange rates create uncertainty for both firms and employees (EIU, 2023).

Labor dynamics further complicate the sector. Many manufacturers report difficulties accessing credit, securing land, and navigating regulatory systems. Performance pressures from global buyers, especially in labor-intensive industries like apparel, contribute to unfair labor conditions and informal practices. Programs such as Better Work Egypt highlight ongoing concerns related to labor rights and workplace standards (Better Work Egypt, 2022).

Because manufacturing work relies heavily on coordination, discipline, and quality control, perceived fairness is especially crucial. Employees who feel fairly treated exhibit higher morale, trust, and cooperation, which enhances production outcomes (Saks, 2006). Conversely, perceived injustice leads to absenteeism, low quality output, safety risks, and resistance to change. Cultural factors in Egypt, characterized by collectivism and high power distance, amplify the importance of interactional justice, as respectful treatment from supervisors often has a disproportionate influence on fairness judgments (Local Understandings of Decent Work, 2024). These contextual considerations justify the examination of justice, trust, and engagement within Egypt's manufacturing sector.

Measurement Tools

Colquitt's Organizational Justice Scale

This study measures perceived organizational justice using Colquitt's (2001) 20-item scale, which evaluates distributive, procedural, interpersonal, and informational justice. It is one of the most validated and widely applied justice measures in organizational research. Each item employs a Likert-type response format, enabling

quantitative analysis of employee fairness perceptions. The scale's strong reliability (Cronbach's alpha > .80 across dimensions) and cross-cultural validation (Colquitt et al., 2001) make it appropriate for capturing justice perceptions across diverse industrial settings. In this study, the scale serves as the primary measure for the independent variable.

Gallup Q12 Employee Engagement Scale

Employee engagement is measured using the Gallup Q12, a standard instrument assessing core dimensions of workplace engagement, including expectations, resources, recognition, development, mission clarity, and relationships (Gallup, 2023). The Q12 is widely used in organizational diagnostics due to its strong predictive validity for business outcomes such as profitability, productivity, and turnover (Harter, Schmidt, & Hayes, 2002). Its conceptual alignment with SDT and SET further supports its use in this study, as the items reflect psychological needs and reciprocal relational dynamics (Saks, 2006).

Measuring Organizational Trust: Mayer and Davis Scale

Organizational trust is measured using the 21-item scale developed by Mayer and Davis (1999), assessing competence, benevolence, integrity, predictability, and intention to act. The scale employs Likert-type items and has been validated across numerous organizational studies (Colquitt, Scott, & LePine, 2007). Trust is conceptualized as a multidimensional construct, and strong trust in management is linked to higher engagement, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment (Dirks & Ferrin, 2002). Its inclusion as a mediating variable aligns with theoretical expectations regarding fairness mechanisms.

Reliability and Validity Overview

Reliability analysis using Cronbach's alpha demonstrated high reliability across all scales, with values ranging from 0.89 to 0.94, exceeding the accepted threshold of 0.7 for internal consistency (Hinton et al., 2004; Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994). Internal consistency validity was confirmed through significant item-total correlations across all dimensions, indicating that items consistently measured their intended constructs. Face validity was established through expert review by faculty members at the Faculty of Business, ESLSCA University, ensuring clarity and relevance of questionnaire items.

Applications in Organizational Research

The measurement tools adopted in this study have been widely applied in organizational research examining fairness, trust, and engagement. Studies frequently demonstrate that high levels of perceived justice and trust predict stronger organizational commitment, higher performance, improved job satisfaction, and greater collaboration (Dirks & Ferrin, 2002; Colquitt et al., 2007). These validated tools therefore strengthen the methodological rigor of the present research and support generalizable conclusions about justice and engagement dynamics.

Research Design: Population, Sampling, & Unit of Analysis

A probability random sampling technique was employed, with the population defined as employees in Egypt's manufacturing sector. The population is considered unknown and unlimited, and data were collected using online surveys. The convenience sampling component ensured broad access to participants across diverse manufacturing settings.

The individual employee serves as the unit of analysis. This level of analysis enables examination of how personal perceptions of justice relate to individual engagement levels. Because fairness perceptions often vary based on job roles, supervisory experiences, and workplace interactions, the individual level is most appropriate for capturing these nuanced differences (Klein & Kozlowski, 2000).

Manufacturing employees represent a critical segment of Egypt's workforce and often operate within structured, hierarchical environments where justice perceptions are salient (Central Bank of Egypt, 2022). The

sector's size and diversity provide a relevant context for examining justice dimensions. The online survey method facilitated efficient data collection across a large and geographically dispersed workforce (Dillman et al., 2014).

Data Collection Overview

Structured surveys were distributed electronically to gather quantitative data on justice perceptions, engagement, and organizational trust. Reliability testing using Cronbach's alpha ensured internal consistency across all scales. Descriptive statistics, including means, standard deviations, and variances, were calculated to examine data distribution patterns. These analyses provided the foundation for subsequent inferential statistical testing.

Research Approach

The research adopts a positivist paradigm, emphasizing objective measurement, empirical testing, and generalizable findings (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2019). Positivism supports hypothesis development grounded in established theory and validation through statistical analysis (Bryman, 2016).

Positivism assumes an objective reality that can be measured and analyzed through scientific methods. This philosophical stance aligns with the study's goal of identifying quantifiable relationships among justice, trust, and engagement. The survey method was selected for its ability to collect large quantities of quantifiable data from diverse respondents, supporting statistical testing and generalization (Fowler, 2014).

A cross-sectional design was selected to capture a snapshot of employee perceptions at a specific point in time. This design is efficient and appropriate for examining current relationships among variables (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe, & Jackson, 2015).

Data collection relied on structured questionnaires, consistent with positivist principles and allowing consistent comparison across respondents. This method contributes to reliability and supports objective analysis through statistical tools such as SPSS and AMOS (Collis & Hussey, 2013).

Data Collection and Analysis

This chapter presents the results of the statistical analyses conducted to examine the impact of perceived organizational justice (POJ) on employee engagement (EE), with organizational trust (OT) serving as a mediating variable. Data were prepared in MS Excel and analyzed using SPSS and AMOS. The analyses include validity and reliability assessments, descriptive statistics, normality testing, regression analysis, and mediation analysis.

Validity and Reliability Analysis

Face validity was established through expert review to ensure item clarity and relevance. Internal consistency validity was assessed using Pearson correlations, demonstrating strong item-total correlations across all constructs. Reliability analysis using Cronbach's alpha indicated high reliability, with values above 0.89 for all scales, confirming statistical adequacy for further analysis.

Descriptive Data Analysis

Demographic Characteristics

The sample consisted of 384 participants, with a near-balanced gender distribution: 198 males (51.6%) and 186 females (48.4%). Age distribution was concentrated in the groups aged 36–45 years (35.4%) and 46–55 years (40.6%), reflecting the predominance of mid-career and late-career employees. Most participants (87%) worked at the operational level, with 13% holding managerial roles.

Descriptive Statistics of Justice Dimensions

Procedural justice showed moderate to high agreement, with mean scores ranging from 3.49 to 4.07. Distributive justice displayed similar trends, with means between 3.89 and 3.98. Interactional justice exhibited the strongest positive perceptions, with means between 4.00 and 4.36. These results indicate that employees perceive interpersonal treatment as the most favorable justice dimension, followed by distributive and procedural justice.

Inferential Data Analysis

Normality Testing

Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests indicated that all variables were normally distributed ($p > 0.05$), supporting the use of parametric statistical tests.

Regression Analysis: Testing Hypotheses

Regression analysis confirmed that perceived organizational justice significantly predicted employee engagement ($R^2 = 0.52$). Procedural justice had the strongest effect ($\beta = 0.531$), followed by interactional justice ($\beta = 0.190$) and distributive justice ($\beta = 0.124$).

Similarly, perceived organizational justice significantly predicted organizational trust ($R^2 = 0.46$), with interactional justice ($\beta = 0.337$) and procedural justice ($\beta = 0.326$) showing the strongest effects.

Organizational trust significantly predicted employee engagement ($\beta = 0.74$), accounting for 51% of the variance in engagement.

Mediation Analysis

Mediation analyses using Baron and Kenny's approach and bootstrapping confirmed partial mediation of OT in all three justice dimensions:

Distributive justice	→	EE:	29.5%	mediation
Procedural justice	→	EE:	41.1%	mediation
Interactional justice → EE: 43.1% mediation				

These results demonstrate that organizational trust strengthens the association between perceived fairness and engagement.

Conclusion, Recommendations, and Implications

The findings reveal a strong relationship between perceived organizational justice and employee engagement, with organizational trust serving as a critical mediating mechanism. Distributive, procedural, and interactional justice all significantly influence engagement, and these effects are enhanced through trust. Organizations seeking to improve engagement must prioritize fairness and trust-building initiatives.

Research Findings

Statistical analyses provide strong empirical support for the conceptual framework and hypotheses. Procedural justice exerted the strongest impact on engagement, highlighting the importance of transparent and unbiased processes. Interactional justice also played a major role, underscoring the value employees place on respectful treatment. Distributive justice demonstrated a meaningful, though comparatively smaller, effect.

The mediating role of organizational trust aligns with SET and JD-R by demonstrating that fairness perceptions strengthen trust, which in turn increases engagement. These results extend justice and engagement theories to a non-Western industrial context and highlight fairness as a strategic resource in manufacturing environments.

Recommendations for Organizational Practice

Organizations should enhance procedural fairness by standardizing decision-making processes, communicating criteria transparently, and providing appeals mechanisms. Distributive fairness should be strengthened through equitable reward and recognition systems aligned with performance. Interactional fairness must be prioritized by training supervisors in communication, emotional intelligence, and conflict management. Building trust requires leaders to demonstrate integrity, competence, consistency, and benevolence. Continuous monitoring of fairness and engagement perceptions is essential for timely interventions.

Policy-Making Implications

Human resource policies should institutionalize fairness principles across evaluation, promotion, and grievance systems. Leadership development programs must emphasize trust-building competencies. National policies could promote justice training across industries, and labor regulations could integrate organizational justice criteria to improve workplace standards. Cultural shifts toward transparency and participation would further enhance engagement outcomes.

Practical Implications

The study provides a roadmap for improving engagement through structured interventions in procedural, distributive, and interactional justice, supported by trust-building practices. Managers and policymakers can use these insights to cultivate organizational cultures that enhance motivation, productivity, and retention.

Research Limitations

Limitations include the cross-sectional design, which restricts causal inference; the focus on the manufacturing sector, which limits generalizability; the absence of cultural variables; and the need to explore additional mediators and moderators. These limitations highlight opportunities for expanding the study in future research.

Future Research Suggestions

Future studies should adopt longitudinal designs, conduct cross-cultural comparisons, examine alternative sectors, incorporate additional psychosocial variables, explore justice dynamics during organizational change, and analyze the role of remote work in shaping justice and trust perceptions.

Conclusion

This study confirms that perceived organizational justice significantly influences employee engagement in Egypt's manufacturing sector and that organizational trust serves as a critical mediating factor. Procedural justice exerted the strongest influence, followed by interactional and distributive justice. Fair processes, equitable outcomes, and respectful treatment contribute to stronger trust and higher engagement, validating SET and JD-R assumptions. The findings have substantial implications for leadership practice, HR policy, and organizational development, especially in hierarchical and labor-intensive contexts. By fostering fairness and trust, organizations can cultivate engaged, committed, and high-performing employees, contributing to sustainable success and national economic development.

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